

Exploring Communicative Skills as Workforce for Dynamic Entrepreneurship

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ABSTRACT

Acquisition of skills and its continual development may be considered as a defining element for the growth story of India, where we need to explore its integration with education. If we look back at the conventional model of education, we find that the success of those students totally depends on, what we don't see are the countless hours they consumed behind the divisions, improving their expertise, and edifying their skills. Today's Indian workforce is massively talented and adaptable. It focuses not only on economic, infrastructure and technical development but also tend to lead the nation towards industrial development, giving a global recognition in Indian Industry. The present paper explores how the institution, employer, and government need to collaborate to make sure that the employability skill honed by the graduates of higher learning institutions match with the needs of the industry and its job requirements. The study aims to consider the place of skills in the universities to draw a suggested framework with an initiative that may be introduced to promote such skills for dynamic entrepreneurship.

Keywords: skills, skill development, entrepreneurship, smart India, higher education

INTRODUCTION

Employability is known as an amalgamation of expertise, knowledge and personal traits that makes an individual employable. Even the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) today are examining and exercising on the approaches and measures to enhance and strengthen students' employability skills. Fabricating the graduates that are employable encompasses full educational variability of values, from imparting knowledge and understanding of developing skills and attributes. Employability skills are more 'service oriented'. So the question here is what has actually been the reason/s leading to the prioritization of institutions? Today the research is being put forward to cultivate employability at higher education level, pushing employers towards demanding skills from graduates. In fact, the employers today focus more on the practical and generic skills of graduates than an actual / technical degree earned. The success of an organization is pivoted around the quantity and quality of information that flows in the form of technical communication. In the present arena of technocrats and engineering advancements, technical communication acts as a stimulant for engineers to be persuasive, expressive, influential and competent (Mishra & Mishra, 2020). Generic skills are important because the labor market is intensely competitive, and the employers look for flexibility, tendency of taking initiatives and an ability to face challenges impending from a variety of tasks in different environments. They generally observe a graduate's accomplishment related to the subject discipline as a necessity. Every generation forms its own demonstration of trans-cultural identity (Mishra & Mishra, 2018). Accomplishments outside the precincts of the discipline like work experience, involvement in clubs; volunteering and social service are considered to have equal importance in this context as compared to academia. The 'employability agenda' might lay a decisive implication for any leading university, and there is little doubt that it imposes an impact on student recruitment, retention, and satisfaction. Prospective students as well as parents carefully weigh up their future employment scenarios consult university league tables referring graduate destination data and starting salaries while selecting degrees and institution's employability performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Over past decades lot of researches have been done on employability. In (1998), Hillage and Pollard gave the term employability and explained it as an individual's capability to gain and retain employment, switch between the roles and jobs to

obtain new employment. In their research they emphasize on “skills based solutions to social hardship”. The research was further expanded by Gazier (2001), which suggests that employability is conditioned in labor-market, which focuses on individual, and supply related solutions, and also involves the interaction between the individual and other surrounding people. The Higher Education Academy and the Enhancing Student Employability Co-ordination Team (ESECT) defines employability as: “A set of skills, knowledge and personal attributes that make an individual more likely to secure and be successful in their chosen occupation(s) to the benefit of them, the workforce, the community and the economy.” Yorke (2006) defined employability as a set of personal, understanding and achievements-skills, which help graduates to achieve more success in their chosen career. Later, McQuaid and Lindsay (2005) suggest the concept and importance of employability to native, national and international labor market policy. A researcher, Gravels (2010) explained that employability is nothing but skills which help people to get employment. In (2017), Selvam said that employability is skills which include written and verbal communication, planning, teamwork, adaptability, learning skills and technical skills. Later he further expanded his research to discover the promoting factors of employability skills, i.e., confidence, group experiences, industrial interactions, participating in co-curricular activities etc.

METHODOLOGY

The study aimed to explore what are the reasons and how a trainer trains employability skills as a subject in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The ancient informative tools are being used for training the students to teach the subject whereas the teachers have described the case studies for this subject is used partially only. So, we need to adhere to some other methods like Role plays, executive games, recreations, exercises related to new venture creation, analytical and creative thinking exercises, focusing on individuals' innovative approach to invigorate the entrepreneurial minds. Here the fact lies in that majority are not even aware about such approaches or never heard about the crowd tracking as a means to augment their curriculum and content. So, for this descriptive study the data have been collected from various organizations with regard to their teaching curriculum and prominent pedagogy to teach employability skills to their graduates and their perceptions about the subject itself in Indian universities.

FINDINGS

Communicative Skills: As a Performance Indicator

Employability has become an article of trade, meticulously associated to government policies in which students showcase a valuable resource in the progressive form of knowledge based economy. We may observe it as a large form of debate related to the definition of employability. There is a widespread covenant that Employability is not just about receiving a job. The present status of the employability program within Higher Education System is to meet the Employer Needs. Progressively, today the employers are demanding skills, knowledge and expertise from graduates which are outside the subject area of study in Higher Education. Traditional societies continue to be treated as objects, like machinery, which can be made desirably functional by replacing some old parts with new ones. (Mishra, 2018) Today's Indian workforce is massively talented and adaptable. Employability is frequently spoken about with regard to the ranking of organizations/ institutes in the University league tables, wherein employability is used as a performance indicator connecting to the employment rates of graduates. Institutional support is grossly lacking in teaching which accounts to a large extent to the dismal state of teaching methodologies and the lack of creativity in teaching which is essential as much is air and water to survive. (Gandhi, 2017) Employability when considered as skills, knowledge and attributes seems totally rational, but argues about the nature of personal attributes. Development of technical knowledge and skills has been the prime motive of conventional engineering curriculum but today both written and spoken communication skills are the primary assets for the professionals to get engaged with other professional groups (Mishra & Mishra, 2017). Personal attributes is an extensive category of skill that suggests an 'x factor' component depending on the personality and nature catering outside the stimulus of our academic institutes. Indeed, some employers have placed less importance on graduates' technical degree when it comes to comparison with generic skills. Employers generally see a graduate's accomplishment related to the subject discipline as necessary which at times are not sufficient for them to be recruited. Achievements outside the boundaries of the discipline like owning the so-called 'soft skills' are generally considered to be significant in the recruitment of graduates. Suggestively, extra-curricular activities such as work experience, undertaking social work and involvement in clubs and societies are seen as having equal importance in this context as the knowledge and experience acquired through academic study. Employability Skills in this context here focus on the set of skills that are identified as a fundamental element of graduate employability.

Expansion of Skills: As a Support System

According to Alan Warner, Words are the tools of thought. If they become rusty and dirty, and lose their sharp points and cutting edges, thinking it becomes keen and efficient. Man needs language for the control of his environment, and the fluent his language, the better his control. Need for being competent in engineering education is a must for an engineer as it is recognized in several places worldwide. Consequently, only competent, capable and committed communicator, having good command over languages of communication will be able to compete in the race of exhibiting his professional expertise culminating into powerful place in society. (Mishra, 2017). More than 60% of employers have specified that language skills whether written or oral should be mandated for jobs in their companies as there is a lack of bilingual skilled workforce in graduate occupation. Although among bilinguals, proficiency in written and oral communication varies widely, the existing graduates have had some form of language

education, not all do regard themselves as fluent speakers of the language. Research has suggested that while bilingualism is not the realm of front-runners, untrained graduates may believe that their form of bilingualism is incompatible for professional milieus. (Shankar, 2012) thus quotes that there are six primary obstacles that could be classified to teaching employability skills to Indian graduates: Lack of institutionalization; Lack of indigenous experience; Lack of trained teachers; Short-term focus on results; Limitations with content pedagogy and Subject hasn't been considered as core.

A number of interviewees felt a lack of confidence in their language skills as they felt that they spoke in regional accent which was not the same as the prescribed one, desirable for employment drives. Undoubtedly, Universities need to support and nurture the abilities of their graduates not just by focusing on generic employability skills, but also by looking at their language skills too. If we think rationally, we find what local employers might want from graduates; organizations may initiate to address those academic, financial and social hurdles to the modern graduates. These elements of exchangeable skills, play a dynamic role for attainment of graduate employability and that their absence seriously challenges its other aspects.

Ethical Values and Soft Skills: As Stakes of Employability

We all aspire for a happy and successful life. Through the correct implementation of education, we prove to be competent in our workplace. It is only education that helps us to envisage our goals correctly and shows the path towards their fulfillment. Integrity, edification and skills are interrelated in the world of employability.

Employability skills are the key competencies or are those elementary skills necessary for receiving, possessing, and creating well in a profession. Integrity teaches us how one ought; or ought not to perform; or about some end-state of existence worth or not worth attaining. The values of ethics and usage of skills make us professionally strong when it comes to choice and decision making. Self-awareness, self-exploration, introspection, risk-management, materialistic and non-materialistic satisfaction at workplace comes only by carrying out ethical values and soft skills. In order to achieve the competitive advantage and lead the professional race, we need to have some attributes like commitment, motivation, and perspiration.

As the technology and information system continues to prosper, the world needs to be aware of ethical issues related to these technical developments. Also, every job-seeker/student is expected to have some pertinent skills like communication and interpersonal skills; leadership skills; cultural transactions; creative thinking; technical skills; reasoning; competency and efficiency; teamwork and managerial skills, multi-tasking skills. Technological trends are an area that deserves a lot of attention while discussing ethical behavior in the business world.

CONCLUSION

This paper showcases the harsh reality of the scenario of employability skills honed by graduates coming from Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). One major problem for the graduate is when it comes down to the skills that employers really need from potential employees, they lack in those due to their regional impression. As it is not sufficient just to have a professional degree in hand, similarly it is not sufficient to teach all graduates same generic set of skills; it must be according to their personal capabilities as well. Essential skills may vary from one area to another or may be depending upon their expertise. No doubt, they must be reinvigorated to enhance their skills such as attributes towards problem solving; self-management; and the ability to work as a team. Also the policy makers are required to intervene with concern to investment in training of teachers and providing them an opportunity to groom and update themselves with regard to the best practices and upcoming trends being used to nurture employability skills of the graduates resulting in dynamic leadership. It is also related to the great insight of work satisfaction, effective work relationships, enhanced communication, quality management in terms of health outcomes and less work stress and greater perceived wellness (Manshi & Mishra, 2019).

A good amount of research shows that the mixing of skills with degree frameworks is not essential for all the Universities to thrive. But it is essential for students to know the importance of Employability Skills, for which they need to move and think out of the box. But the truth is that not every graduate wants to or is able to leave the University town or city, especially females and graduates from low-income backgrounds. They are usually reminded that a degree is "not enough", but are they really aware that this requires "employability skills" – which is an intricate combination of personality traits, soft skills, language skills, ethical values, discipline specific knowledge and generic talents – to succeed actually after the University life. Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) should now start planning a longitudinal study of graduate journey. Then only the capability of graduates may be measured and they will be capable of responding to the change and the demands of this fast developing market which is observed as vital for economic growth.

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